

WASHBACK IN LANGUAGE TEACHING ASSESSMENT

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Annotation:

“Washback” (alternatively “backwash”) is a term used in education to describe the influence, whether beneficial or damaging, of an assessment on the teaching and learning that precedes and prepares for that assessment. The purpose of this scientific work is to comment on the use of "Washback" used as a type of assessment in language teaching and its important aspects.

Key words: washback, extensive research, backwash, concept, macrofactor, positive teaching, negative teaching.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past 30 years, washback, often conceived as one instance of “impact” or the range of effects that assessment may have on society more generally, has become established as a popular topic for applied linguistics research.¹ Studies have covered a variety of contexts from national and international tests administered to millions of test takers to the classroom assessment practices of individual teachers. Researchers have employed a range of methods, including small-scale observational studies and much more extensive

¹ <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9781405198431.wbeal1274.pub2>

questionnaire surveys, often making use of mixed methods to access different perspectives on the issues. These have revealed washback to be a complex phenomenon, closely associated with and affected by established practices, beliefs, and attitudes. Although test developers increasingly recognize the importance of washback and impact in evaluating assessment use, it remains to be fully integrated into standard validation practice.

Washback, a concept prominent in applied linguistics, refers to the extent to which the introduction and use of a test influences language teachers and learners to do things they would not otherwise do that promote or inhibit language learning.²

“Washback” is a topic and concept that has been the subject of extensive research by many applied linguists in various educational contexts over the past three decades. In fact, like Cheng et al. (2015) note: “In the last 20 years, no field of language assessment research has received more attention than Washback ”(p. 436). Although there is a general debate among researchers about the existence of Washback, opinions on the exact definition of this concept are very diverse.

METHODOLOGY

Some researchers narrow the interaction between teachers and students in the classroom (e.g., Alderson & Wall, 1993; Bailey, 1996; Messick, 1996), while others argue that ‘outside the classroom has a broader perspective on the phenomenon that pervades society as a whole’. promote views (e.g., Brown and Hudson, 1998; Andrew et al., 2002). It is noteworthy that some researchers (e.g., Bachman & Palmer, 1996; Hamp-Lyons, 1997) distinguish between “test backwash” and “test effect,” looking at washback as an “impact” aspect, the second is that “trials are any influence that may affect individuals, policies, or practices in the classroom, school, education system, or society as a whole” (Wall,

² <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.117>

1997, p. 291). However, for the purposes of this study, “Washback” and exposure are used interchangeably because the main focus is limited to the language class. The definition of the term washback is “at the level of the introduction and application of the test influences language teachers and learners to do things that encourage or do not stop language learning ”(Messick, 1996, p. 243).

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Washback has been described as “the effect of tests on teaching and learning” according to the theories of Chen (2002) and Hughes (2003). However, Cheng and Curtis (2004) clearly distinguish between washback and test effects. The test effect refers to the effect of the test on “individuals, policies, or practices within the classroom” (p. 4). Andrews, Fullilove, and Wong (2002) believe that this headlight does not change and that “narrower and wider effects can be introduced under the term washback” (cited in Salehi et al (2011)). The concept of washback should be related to life and real situations. Cheng (2000) refers to the validity of washback to describe “the quality of the relationship between testing and teaching and learning” (p. 4). The type of assessment finds its proof, especially when the results are used for important decisions. Accordingly, Salehi et al (2011) argue that “only real tests that minimize design inconsistencies can increase the chances of a positive repetition.” 2008) supports this idea. In his detailed study, when and if teachers shorten any aspect of the curriculum due to tests, it leads to a negative washback. (Tylor, 2005) Knowing how reversal occurs Manjarres (2009) argues that “a number of variables in society, education, and schools” need to be taken into account. process variables and variables related to the quality of the object and product studied takes a (Hughes, 1993, Bailey, 1996). Different scientists interpret washback differently due to different results of washback. Alderson and Wall (1993) show that English language tests lead to “faster changes in teaching content than changes in teaching methodology” (Manjarres, 2009). Cheng (1997) believes that a tool that leads to changes in teaching materials is a washback.

Andrews et al. (2002) found that “washback is primarily related to“ high-cost ”tests, that is, tests used to make important decisions”. The current washback has been introduced into the education system to improve teaching and learning. Saif, (2000). In addition, Shohamy et al. (1996) “considered other features such as the status of the test subject, the nature of the test, and the application of test scores.” Wall (1996) also looked at factors ranging from teacher factors to more macrofactors lists other characteristics, such as “the gap between test designers and teachers, the lack of well-trained teachers, and the overload of teachers.” According to Andrew et al. (2002), motivation and published. materials should be included as washback factors.

Researchers often discuss test processing as ‘negative’ or ‘positive’, leading to discussions as to whether they adequately hinder or encourage language development. According to Alderson and Wall (1993), as well as Cheng and Curtis (2004), tests, and especially language tests, are often suspected to have a negative impact on teaching and learning or to “negative washback” . Similarly, Vernon (1956) and Davies (1968) are responsible for making it necessary for students to use “examination methods rather than language learning activities” to cause exams to disrupt the curriculum and make the learning experience limited and boring. (Wiseman 1961, p. 159). Noble and Smith (1994) continue their ideas and ideas on the use of tests in teaching, especially high-level tests of great importance to individuals and institutions, which have a direct and negative impact on teachers. and “emphasizes the teaching of exam skills. Optional sheets on test sheets can increase scores, but may not increase overall understanding” (p. 6). According to Brown (2002), when there is a discrepancy between the test or between the content and the test, the “washback becomes negative” (p. 12). change leads to improved learning and teaching practices. Pearson (1988) believes that tests can serve as a “support for change” (p. 101) and as a tool for improving curricula and teaching. Alderson (1986) noted a potential washback.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The number of tests is determined by their properties and application. Based on this interpretation, “if a bad test has a negative effect, a good test should or may have a positive washback” (Alderson & Banerjee, 2001, p. 214). As Bachman (1990) points out, a useful washback occurs when the exam represents the content and skills taught in the classroom. Also, from the point of view of washback proponents, training can be a test.

Positive washback

If the test represents a curriculum, it can be considered an incentive for curriculum reform (Noble and Smith, 1994). It is important to note that the so-called “curriculum-learning” by Popham (2001, p. 16) is “test-based teaching” in which teachers use their guidelines to convey a specific content of knowledge. 'redirects to a plan or a specific set'. cognitive abilities expressed by a given test. ”This should be clearly distinguished from“ test teaching ”or“ object teaching ”where“ teachers place their instructions around or similar to real things found in the test. organize around a set of things ”(Popham, 2001, p. 16). According to Messick (1996), if the classroom work is the same as the things used in the test, the probability of a positive washback increases:” for optimal positive washback, there should be very little difference between language learning efforts and, if available, the need to prepare for an exam ”(pp. 241–242). Furthermore, Messick (1996) increases the probability of a positive washback if the tests include benchmark samples: ridan-straight samples ”(p. 241), which is minimized. There are "two main threats to the creation of reality" (p. 247) - "low representation" and "construction-insignificant".

Neutral views were also included, in particular Alderson and Wall (1993) that “washback quality may not depend on test quality” (p. 118). They point out that factors other than test properties can also affect the absence or presence of a washback, which highlights the need to differentiate between washback effects

and other effects. Given the complexity of training and its susceptibility to the influence of various factors, Messick (1996) argues that only effects that are clearly related to the test should be considered a washback: “washback is the result of a test if it if possible, it confirms its validity. It should be clear that this is the effect of the test, not of other forces acting on the educational scene ”(p. 242). However, it warns against confusing washback arguments with weak arguments, or good teaching and "... positive teaching-related positive teaching, regardless of the quality of the test, negative teaching, negative teaching." emphasizes the need for differentiation (Messick, 1996, p. 243).

Negative Washback

It can be argued that the mock exam creates negative washback since there is a focus on certain parts of the curriculum and does not provide enough content to cover the whole program. While on the other hand, the weekly quizzes cover all content in each chapter and does allow for positive washback since it covers all the chapters of the program. Ideally in any program, the goal is to provide a balanced teaching and learning experience to learners.

Cordeur (2014) looked at the paradigm shift in education, from learning from content to teaching for the test. The education system has placed great emphasis on standardized tests as a means of measuring learners’ performance. Both students and teachers spend too much time preparing for the exam and this has come at the expense of a broader educational experience. The same can be said with any program that relies heavily on standardized tests to measure learners’ performance. Teachers are expected to have their students perform well on these tests and students only want to learn content relating to the test. These expectations make it difficult for balanced teaching and learning. This environment makes it desirable for teachers to just coach for the test. Thus, while coaching students may lead to higher scores on exams, it comes at the price. According to Cordeur, drilling students to pass the test results in a narrow

curriculum, poorer quality of teaching and education. Cordeur conducted an empirical study on whether an increased pass rate on standardized tests is an effective indication of improved learning and quality teaching with special focus on literacy.

CONCLUSION

The researcher investigated historical educational issues, thereby gaining valuable insights on changes leading to the current education system. The researcher found that focusing on standardized tests has deflected the issue of low literacy rates in the country. This research is important because constantly tasking teachers and learners with more tests, will not necessarily lead to enhanced educational outcomes. Language programs must start to move away from teaching for the test to a more holistic approach to teaching. Teaching for the test can lead to teaching practice directed to ignoring or narrowing down the syllabus to solely address the needs of the students to pass the final test. This can lead to classroom practices that are oriented towards the direction set by the final test. This can result in a lack of general awareness of the importance of improving all the required skills for learning English.

Moreover, the direction set by the test determines what is taught and what is ignored in class. For instance, the findings of the study indicate that the teachers' decisions relevant to syllabus, tasks, and quizzes are all because of the final test that cannot necessarily assure students of the wider general goal of learning English.

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